

Unveiling Gender Disparities in Post-Purchase Evaluation: Evidence from Kolkata During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Rupa Mondal

Ph.D. Research Scholar, University of Calcutta, Kolkata

Email: rugarow11@gmail.com

and

Supti Kotal

Associate Professor, Maharaja Srischandra College, Kolkata

Email: profsuptik.sardar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study introspects gender disparities in the context of post-purchase evaluation between customers in Kolkata during the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, it also studies the proportion of the effect made by individual variables on gender in the context of post-purchase evaluation. A total of 384 responses were collected using convenient sampling techniques from consumers of Kolkata using Cochran's formula of an unknown population. Different statistical tests like Cronbach's alpha, Mann-Whitney test, and the principal component analysis are applied along with frequencies and cross-tabulation. Cronbach's alpha provides an acceptable value indicating the accuracy of the measurement. The Mann-Whitney test further confirms that there exists a difference between males and females in the context of post-purchase evaluation. The principal component analysis provides the loadings of the effect made by the variables. Hence, it is concluded that when it comes to assessing goods and services after making a purchase, men and women may have distinct viewpoints and behaviours. Hence, the companies should adopt the necessary policies to better appeal to each group once they have a better grasp of the variations in post-purchase assessment behaviour between men and women.

Keywords: Consumers, post-purchase evaluation, Cronbach alpha, Cochran, Mann-Whitney

A. Introduction

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there have been major alterations in consumer behaviour, resulting in frantic purchasing and hoarding of necessary things. Such changes have not only impacted the “economy”, but have also created opportunities for further research. With the outbreak of the pandemic, consumers have become more cautious about their purchasing decisions, and many have shifted to online platforms for their shopping needs. The global economy has

also been significantly impacted by the pandemic, with many businesses suffering huge losses as a result of decreased demand and supply chain disruptions. In this context, understanding consumer behaviour during the pandemic has become crucial for businesses to survive and thrive in the current market.

Past research has looked into individual panic buying from a number of perspectives, including as judicial and governmental responses (Kobayashi and Anbumozhi, 2016), vendors and merchants (Shou et al., 2011), vaccines purchased in a panic (Godlee, 2010), and catastrophes of nature (Thomas and Mora, 2014). Certain studies indicate that it's critical to comprehend how social media influences consumers' behaviour and intent to buy (Aragoncillo and Orus, 2018), along with their propensity for rash purchases (Chung et al., 2017).

Despite the fact that these studies have illuminated consumer stockpiling behaviour, there is still a dearth of thorough studies focusing on how consumer psychology influences panic buying in the event of a pandemic (Liren et al., 2012; Sheth, 2020; Yuen et al., 2020). Since then, everything in life has moved extremely swiftly, from toilet paper to plane tickets, as a result of globalization and digitization, making people, places, and things more accessible and affordable. A mouse click was all it took to do this. When COVID-19 was made public, all business travel, meetings, and planning were discontinued. People were prompted to consider how families have altered their expenditures and online purchases in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the characteristics of the households who have responded most quickly and vehemently. News reports claim that customers stocked up on durable products during supermarket deals (Sharma and Jhamb, 2020).

Thus, it is necessary for us to conduct a thorough empirical investigation in order to the waygender differences are noted for post-purchase evaluation throughout the COVID-19 outbreak.

B. Objective of the Study

This study intends to investigate the disparities in the post-purchase evaluations of consumers throughout the COVID-19 outbreak, concentrating especially on Kolkata.

C. Literature Survey

The review of the literature is covered in this part, the gap in research, and the study's goals. Extant kinds of literature have been studied from both national and international contexts with some interesting outcomes highlighted below.

Basu et al. (2023) intend to shed light on whether Immersion Film may employ as well as mimic OTT platforms' digital simulation of the real world to achieve legitimacy inside a cutthroat market for entertainment. To get insight into opinions on the possibility of Immersion viewing on OTT platforms in comparison to conventional theatrical releases, the authors held focus groups with fourteen MBA candidates and performed qualitative, semi-structured interviews with twenty-one customers. As a direct substitute for theatrical releases, OTT services are able to select which new releases using the study findings.

Mondal et al. (2023) used principal component analysis to conduct an empirical evaluation of the determinants influencing consumers buying behaviour towards purchasing decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on Kolkata. Using a practical sample technique, the study was carried out between August 29, 2022, and February 6, 2023. When analyzing the data with IBM SPSS Statistics 21, various statistical tests are utilized, including the principal component analysis (PCA), Cronbach's alpha, and frequency statistics. Both primary and secondary research is being done. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is substantial and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is near 1. In addition, 9 components were obtained from 38 questions already in use. It was determined as a result that the factors of taste and preferences, deterring offline purchases, after-sale service, purchasing decisions, the function of reference groups, shifts in consumer behaviour, searching for information, the role of family members, and meeting expectations are the crucial factors distressing the purchasing habits of Kolkata residents during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Singh and Basu (2023) tried to make an effort to evaluate the current research landscape, identify areas for future study, and offer research directions. 197 papers on online consumer shopping behaviour were examined using a well-founded systematic methodology based on the TCCM (theory, context, characteristics, and methodology) framework. The results show that the pool of current literature, which focuses primarily on industrialized countries, has a limited application of theories. While studies have mostly focused on areas like groceries and apparel, experimental and survey-based studies were the most popular in terms of approach. The article also makes some recommendations for potential future research areas. It is advised to employ multiple theories to better understand how customers of online shopping embrace technology.

Chawla et al. (2022) tried to determine the aspects of streaming platforms that affect consumer satisfaction in Kolkata City in West Bengal and the connections between those aspects and various streaming services. A formal questionnaire and casual user interaction were used to conduct the survey, which was conducted in Kolkata, West Bengal. Additionally, correspondence analysis may

be used to link customer happiness with streaming platform services to the calibre of those offerings. It was found that several online streaming platforms were well-linked for offering high-quality content with a variety of options, less advertising, with numerous features of the highest calibre at an affordable cost. Additionally, they utilized cluster analysis to identify three clusters that affected viewers of different ages while they watched on different streaming websites.

Girija et al. (2022) investigated the actual experiences of visitors who stayed in low-cost hotels and how the pandemic has altered their target market's expectations. The current study employs ethnography to look assess how customers who stayed in low-cost motels during the COVID-19 outbreak felt about their stays. A thematic analysis of "1,391" customer evaluations gathered from several travel portals was done. The findings revealed that during the COVID-19 epidemic, customization and hygiene were the most important topics that influenced consumer experience. According to the authors, the findings, using contactless services for check-ins and checkouts as well as QR codes found in eateries and other businesses might be beneficial for guests to perceive less danger as well as improve the whole experience of the client.

Srivastava et al. (2022) try to outline the effects of cutting-edge AI-powered technological advancements that will shape the path of the contemporary hospitality sector in the future. These solutions promise strong health-safety measures in hotels and will also assist in developing long-term business and recreational travel infrastructure to deal with scenarios after an epidemic. This study places a strong emphasis on offering a solid technological structure derived from a combination of studies and approaches such might assist lodgings in adopting and implementing cutting-edge AI-driven solutions inside the hotel premises to serve guests with at most hygienic, contactless service, and then pursuing quicker business recovery and winning back consumer trust to encourage reservations in the event of a pandemic. This study offers a technologically oriented approach that would influence the post-pandemic hotel industry. The study contributes to the expansion of the tourism industry by leveraging information management strategies such as contactless hosting, robotic room services, and biosensors. According to the research, the industry will experience a disruptive paradigm shift when robots, RPA technologies, and biosensors are implemented.

Mandal (2021) talked about the shifting customer attitudes and made a comparison of pre- and post-COVID consumer purchasing patterns. The author also looks at the factors that influence consumer decisions. The primary goal is to determine the link between buyers and consumers in the fashion retail market structure. It also enables us to identify the changes that the global community has noticed since the pandemic and its sudden onset.

Shivaprasad (2021) examining the factors that affect e-WOM communication efficiency during the COVID-19 pandemic is essential considering the rise of internet users in India and their use of e-WOM to learn about product information. A model for e-WOM communication and a suitable hypothesis for testing were both offered in the literature review. The conclusion draws attention to the important role that e-WOM variables played in fostering brand image, attitude, and purchase purpose throughout the epidemic. Prior studies have looked at the impact credibility of the message and the source; nonetheless, in e-WOM communication, the website's credibility is seldom considered in conjunction with these constructs. In-depth e-WOM occurrences and factual data from during the COVID-19 era will be covered in this paper. The study's findings will aid practitioners in controlling the impact of e-WOM communication for all stakeholders.

Rajeshwari and Vijay (2020) stated that COVID-19 has caused a significant shift in the world. With reference to Coimbatore City, the current study aims to pinpoint consumer purchasing trends during the epidemic. The primary data was obtained from 315 respondents who answered a structured questionnaire via Google Forms. The researcher edited and used SPSS for data analysis that was gathered concerning the research. Appropriate mathematical and statistical methods, including percentages, means, chi-square tests, and T-tests, have been employed for analysis. At the significance threshold of a p-value of 0.05, a chi-square test was employed to examine the degree of connection among the variables. The study's conclusions indicate that customers' buying patterns have essentially altered, and they are now purchasing fruits and vegetables at a higher cost. The epidemic has also altered consumer preferences for brands.

After minutely examining the existing studies, it can be identified that none of the studies have made any effort to investigate the differences in the purchasing habits of consumers based on the post-purchase evaluation. Moreover, studies in Kolkata are also rarely found. Most of the studies are exploratory with the application of different econometric tools being hard to find. None of the authors have made any effort to study the same throughout the COVID-19 outbreak.

Based on the existing research gaps, the authors decided to study the gender disparities in post-purchase evaluation in the context of Kolkata during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the choice has been taken to ascertain the percentage of different variables that had an impact on gender during the pandemic in terms of post-purchase assessment.

D. Research Methodology

This study falls within the field of marketing where measuring consumer intuition has been attempted. A variety of things can influence consumers' purchasing decisions. The consumers in Kolkata are the main subject of this investigation with the gender discrepancies in post-purchase evaluation during the COVID-19 pandemic. Using primary data, the study is empirical. In order to identify the current research gaps and conduct a theoretical analysis of consumers' opinions, it also incorporates secondary data from various websites in relation to the literature study. A well-structured questionnaire is used to gather primary data from customers in Kolkata, and the data is quantified using a five-point Likert scale. In order to assess customer sentiment, additional secondary data is gathered.

The sample size of 384.16 is obtained by applying Cochran's formula for sample size determination (1977) while taking into account an infinite population.

Where;

Z = determined the required confidence level's crucial value

n_0 = sample size

p = a population's approximate percentage of a certain attribute

q = 1 - p

e = required degree of accuracy

With a 0.05 degree of significance and a 95% confidence level

To include respondents from throughout the city, the Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC) (<https://www.kmcgov.in/KMCPortal/jsp/KMCPortalHome1.jsp>) gathered a total full sample of 384 from 144 wards. The data collection period is from August 29, 2022, to February 6, 2023. The authors made the deliberate choice to use Google Forms to gather the data in light of the impending epidemic. The sample is taken using a convenient stratified representative sampling method. Additionally, the authors choose to use frequency statistics together with other statistical techniques, such as Cronbach's Alpha and Mann-Whitney tests, to analyze the non-parametric data. The principal component analysis (PCA) is also used to investigate the factors that contribute to gender disparities in post-purchase appraisal. The authors also utilized IBM SPSS Statistics 21 to calculate the outcomes of various statistical methods.

Cronbach's Alpha

It is imperative to compute and report the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for internal consistency and reliability for any scales or subscales that are utilized when utilizing Likert-type scales. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient ranges from 0 to 1. The coefficient does not, however, have a lower bound. The

internal consistency of the scale's items is inversely correlated with the Cronbach's alpha coefficient's proximity to 1. Based on the following formula: where k is the number of objects considered and r is the average of the inter-item correlations. How much alpha is created depends on the number of items on the scale and the mean inter-item correlations(<https://scholarworks.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/1805/344/gliem+&+gliem.pdf?sequence=1>). According to George and Mallery (2003), the alpha range of >0.9 is great, >0.8 is good, >0.7 is acceptable, >0.6 is dubious, >0.5 is poor, and <0.5 is unsatisfactory.

Mann-Whitney Test (U)

N.H. (H_0): Both populations are equivalent

A.H. (H_1): Both populations are not equivalent

The Mann-Whitney test formula is as follows:

$$U_1 = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_1(n_1+1)}{2} - R_1$$

$$U_2 = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_2(n_2+1)}{2} - R_2$$

Where;

R_1 = total ranks for the first group

R_2 = total ranks for the second group

If the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected (https://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/mph-modules/bs/bs704_nonparametric/bs704_nonparametric4.html)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The principal component analysis (PCA) concept has been a topic of discussion since antiquity. Almost all scientific fields employ principal component analysis (PCA), which is arguably the most widely utilized multivariate statistical method. It can be the most ancient multivariate method as well. Although Hotelling (1933), who also came up with the phrase "principal component," formalized it, its roots may be found in Pearson (1901), Cauchy (1829), Grattan-Guinness (1997), or Jordan (1874), as well as Boyer and Merzbach (1989). Its goal is to take the most important information from the data table and turn it into a new collection of core components that are orthogonal variables. PCA also depicts the pattern of similarity between them by depicting the variables and observations as dots on maps (Jolliffe, 2002; Jackson, 1991; Saporta and Niang, 2009).

By combining the original variables linearly, principal component analysis (PCA) generates new variables known as principal components. Since this component will "explain" or "extract" the most inertia from the data table, the first principal component must have the most variance (i.e., inertia). To be computed, the second constituent must be orthogonal to the first constituent and have the greatest inertia.

E. Empirical Findings

Frequencies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	185	48.2	48.2	48.2
	Female	199	51.8	51.8	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 1. Gender

The above table represents the results of gender. Out of 384 respondents, 185 are male at 48.2%, and 199 are female at 51.8%.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	80	20.8	20.8	20.8
	Disagree	142	37.0	37.0	57.8
	Neutral	77	20.1	20.1	77.9
	Agree	52	13.5	13.5	91.4
	Strongly Agree	33	8.6	8.6	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 2. After-sale service is provided by the company promptly

The results of the responders to the question "Does the company provide after-sale service promptly?" are displayed in the above table. It can be noticed that 80 respondents 20.8% strongly disagree with the question. Likewise, 142 respondents with 37% disagreed with the question. 77 respondents with 20.7% being neutral to the question. Moreover, 52 respondents with 13.5% agreed with the question, and 33 respondents with 8.6% strongly agreed with question.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	59	15.4	15.4	15.4
	Disagree	102	26.6	26.6	41.9
	Neutral	90	23.4	23.4	65.4
	Agree	62	16.1	16.1	81.5
	Strongly Agree	71	18.5	18.5	100.0

	Total	384	100.0	100.0
--	-------	-----	-------	-------

Table 3. Do not mind paying for service

The above table represents the result of the respondents to the question “Do not mind paying for service”. It can be noticed that 59 respondents with 15.4% strongly disagree with the question. Likewise, 102 respondents with 26.6% disagreed with the question. 90 respondents with 23.4% being neutral to the question. Moreover, 62 respondents with 16.1% agreed with the question, and 71 respondents with 18.5% strongly agreed with question.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	107	27.9	27.9	27.9
	Disagree	167	43.5	43.5	71.4
	Neutral	62	16.1	16.1	87.5
	Agree	16	4.2	4.2	91.7
	Strongly Agree	32	8.3	8.3	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4. Company provides free servicing for a specified period within the warranty

The above table represents the result of the respondents to the question “Company provides free servicing for a specified period within the warranty”. It can be noticed that 107 respondents with 27.9% strongly disagreeing with the question. Likewise, 167 respondents with 43.5% disagreed with the question. 62 respondents with 16.1% being neutral to the question. Moreover, 16 respondents with 4.2% agreed with the question, and 32 respondents with 8.3% strongly agreed with the question.

Cross Tabulation

Count		Question1					Total
		1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	
Gender	1	45	73	35	23	9	185
	2	35	69	42	29	24	199
Total		80	142	77	52	33	384

Table 6. Gender * Question 1 Cross-tabulation

There was a total of 185 respondents who identified as male (1), with 45 responding with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 73 responding with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 35 responding with neutral (3.00) to Question 1,

23 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 9 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question1.

Moreover, out of 199 total female (2) respondents, 35 responded with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 69 responded with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 42 responded with neutral (3.00) to Question 1, 29 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 24 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

Overall, there was a total of 80 respondents who responded with a 1 to Question 1, 142 who responded with a 2, 77 who responded with a 3, 52 who responded with a 4, and 33 who responded with a 5, across both genders.

It has been graphically represented below.

It is inferred that males and females do not believe After-sale service is provided by the company promptly during the COVID-19 pandemic because due to communication delays, Supply Chain Disruptions, and Financialworries. However, males and females do believe that After-sale service is provided by the company promptly during the COVID-19 pandemic because oftwo strong infrastructure, digital solutions, and Customer-Centric attitude.

Count		Question2					Total
		1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	
Gender	1	38	64	39	21	23	185
	2	21	38	51	41	48	199
Total		59	102	90	62	71	384

Table 7. Gender * Question 2 Cross-tabulation

There was a total of 185 respondents who identified as male (1), with 38 responding with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 64 responding with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 39 responding with neutral (3.00 to Question 1, 21 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 23 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

Moreover, out of 199 total female (2) respondents, 21 responded with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 38 responded with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 51 responded with neutral (3.00) to Question 1, 41 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 48 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

Overall, there was a total of 59 respondents who responded with a 1 to Question 1, 102 who responded with a 2, 90 who responded with a 3, 62 who responded with a 4, and 71 who responded with a 5, across both genders.

It has been graphically represented below.

It is inferred that males and females mind to pay for service during the COVID-19 pandemic because due to financial difficulties, Apparent Lack of Value, and change in the habit of spending. On the contrary, they do not mind paying for service during the COVID-19 pandemic because of the endurance of service, social responsibility, and increased safety and security reasons.

Count		Question 3					Total
		1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	
Gender	1	54	93	25	8	5	185
	2	53	74	37	8	27	199
Total		107	167	62	16	32	384

Table 8. Gender * Question 3 Cross-tabulation

There was a total of 185 respondents who identified as male (1), with 54 responding with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 93 responding with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 25 responding with neutral (3.00) to Question 1, 8 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 5 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

Moreover, out of 199 total female (2) respondents, 53 responded with a strongly disagree (1.00) to Question 1, 74 responded with a disagree (2.00) to Question 1, 37 responded with neutral (3.00) to Question 1, 8 responding with an agree (4.00) to Question 1, and 27 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

(4.00) to Question 1, and 27 responding with a strongly agree (5.00) to Question 1.

Overall, there was a total of 107 respondents who responded with a 1 to Question 1, 167 who responded with a 9, 62 who responded with a 3, 16 who responded with a 4, and 32 who responded with a 5, across both genders.

It has been graphically represented below.

It is inferred that males and females do not believe that the Company provides free servicing for a specified period within the warranty during the pandemic because of policy changes, priorities in competing issues, and significant challenges in customer services. Moreover, competitive advantages, commitment towards the community, and company reputation can be the possible reasons that males and females do believe that the Company provides free servicing for a specified period within the warranty during a pandemic.

Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.799	3

Table 9. Reliability Statistics

The results of the 3 questions used to gauge the post-purchase evaluation construct during the COVID-19 pandemic are shown in the above table using Cronbach's alpha. For carrying out the additional research, the Cronbach's alpha of 0.799 is suitable. (George and Mallery, 2003).

Mann-Whitney Test

	Question 1	Question 2	Question 3
Mann-Whitney U	15610.500	13020.000	15710.000
Z	-2.670	-5.075	-2.629
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.008	0.000	0.009
Grouping Variable: Gender			

Table 10. Test Statistics

It can be shown that for every question, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 99% confidence interval with a 1% level of significance. So, this provides the conclusion that there remain discrepancies amongst the genders on the basis of the above-mentioned questions in consumer buying behaviour during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is so because men and women may have different expectations of the products they purchase, which can lead to different post-purchase evaluations. Men may prioritize functionality and efficiency in their purchases, while women may prioritize aesthetics and sensory appeal. Men and women may have different levels of satisfaction with the products they purchase. Women may have higher expectations of the products they purchase and be more critical of any perceived flaws, while men may be more easily satisfied with their purchases. Moreover, women and men may rely on different sources of feedback and reviews when evaluating their purchases which include seeking out reviews and recommendations from friends and family, while men may rely more on expert reviews and ratings. Men and women may have different perceptions of the value of the products they purchase, which can influence their post-purchase evaluation. Women may place a higher value on products that are eco-friendly or socially responsible, while men may prioritize products that are technologically advanced or innovative. Furthermore, men and women may have different levels of emotional attachment to the products they purchase, which can influence their post-purchase evaluation. Women may form emotional attachments to products that they feel are an extension of their identity or personal style, while men may be less emotionally attached to the products they purchase.

Principal Component Analysis

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.701	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	367.459
	df	3
	Sig.	0.000

Table 11. KMO and Bartlett's Test

To assess how well the parts explain one another in terms of the partial correlation between variables, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test is employed. The optimal value for additional factor analysis is nearer to 1. With a test statistic of 0.701, the KMO test shows that factor analysis is possible. Additionally, the result shows that the sample is fantastically enough for conducting a further assessment (<https://www.statisticshowto.com/kaiser-meyer-olkin/>). Bartlett's test of sphericity (1951) is used to determine if the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. With a 99% confidence level, the p-value is 0.00 significant at a 1% level. Consequently, it may be said that there is no identity matrix in the correlation matrix.

	Initial	Extraction
--	---------	------------

After-sale service is provided by the company promptly	1.000	.765
Do not mind pay for the service	1.000	.687
Company provides free servicing for a specified period of time within the warranty	1.000	.697
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Table 12. Communalities

The communality measures how much each variable's variability may be explained by its causes. The ability of the components to explain the variable increases as the communality gets closer to 1. All the variables have a communality value greater than 0.60.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.149	71.626	71.626	2.149	71.626	71.626
2	.486	16.205	87.832			
3	.365	12.168	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

Table 13. Total Variance Explained

The variance explained findings are shown in the above table 5.5.3. The third column has an explanation of each unique variant. 3 variables were used, and a total of 1 variable was retrieved. This 1 component that was retrieved from the model can account for 71.626% of all variations. Additionally, the authors may assert that, following extraction, communalities embody the amount of variance in the individual variable that can be explained by preserved components.

	Component
	1
After-sale service is provided by the company promptly	.874
Do not mind pay for service	.829
The company provides free servicing for a specified period within the warranty	.835
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	
1 component extracted.	

Table 14. Component Matrix

All the components are clubbed into 1 factor which can be named as “post-purchase evaluation with the above-portrayed loadings.

F. Managerial implications

This study provides innumerable significance. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on consumer purchasing behaviour and consume products. By studying gender differences in post-purchase evaluation, the authors can gain insights into how men and women are adapting to these changes differently. This can help businesses and policymakers understand the pandemic's impact on consumer behaviour and tailor their strategies accordingly. Moreover, gender-based disparities in post-purchase evaluation can highlight potential biases in the market. If women consistently rate their purchases lower than men, it could indicate that certain products or services are not meeting women's needs or expectations. By identifying these disparities, businesses can take steps to address them and improve the overall consumer experience. Additionally, by understanding how men and women evaluate their purchases differently, businesses can tailor their customer service and marketing strategies to better meet their customers' needs. If women value personalized customer service more than men, businesses can invest more resources in training their staff to render a more customized service. Increased client satisfaction and loyalty may result from this. Furthermore, gender-based disparities in post-purchase evaluation can also reflect broader social and cultural biases. By identifying and addressing these disparities, businesses, and policymakers can promote gender equality and create a more inclusive marketplace. Hence, studying gender discrepancies in post-purchase evaluation during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kolkata can provide valuable insights into consumer behaviour, help identify disparities in consumer experiences, improve customer satisfaction and loyalty, and promote gender equality.

G. Conclusions and Recommendations

Men and women may have different perspectives and behave differently when it comes to evaluating products and services after making a purchase. These differences might be influenced by a number of factors, including product expectations, customer satisfaction levels, feedback and reviews, value perception, and emotional connection. Companies and marketers may need to take these disparities into account in order to tailor their marketing and product strategies to the needs and preferences of different genders. Knowing the different post-purchase assessment habits of men and women may help businesses better prepare to anticipate and meet the expectations of their customers, increasing satisfaction and loyalty.

A thorough study should be conducted in order for the firms to understand the differences in post-purchase assessment behaviour between men and women. This research may involve polling participants, conducting focus groups,

analysing customer reviews, or gathering data from the social media or online shopping sites on consumer behaviours. Once businesses have a greater understanding of the differences in post-purchase evaluation behaviour between men and women, they may adjust their marketing and advertising strategies to better appeal to each group. To do this, it could be essential to alter the language, tone, and visuals utilised in advertising as well as the venues via which these messages are distributed. Additionally, a company may develop a range of eco-friendly products targeted toward female consumers or provide a variety of cutting-edge products. In addition, a company may develop a line of eco-friendly products targeted toward female customers or provide a range of cutting-edge products for customers that are male. Always ask for feedback from customers after making a purchase, especially for companies. Offering training on gender sensitivity, cultural sensitivity, and how to communicate with clients of all genders might also be a solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to extend their heartfelt appreciation to Dr. Raktim Ghosh, State Aided College Teacher -I, Maharaja Srischandra College, Kolkata, West Bengal, India for his wholehearted technical support and motivation.

References

- Aragoncillo, L., & Orus, C. (2018). Impulse buying behaviour: an online-offline comparative and the impact of social media. *Spanish Journal of Marketing-ESIC*, 22(1), 42-62.
- Basu, A., Mandal, P. C., Murti, A. B., & Makany, T. (2023). Shaping OTT Movie Consumption through Immersive Cinema: A Qualitative Investigation of Consumer Perspectives. *Vision*, 09722629221138375.
- Boyer, C., & Merzbach, U. (1989). A history of mathematics (2nd Edition). New York: Wiley
- Cauchy, A.L. (1829). Sur l'équation à l'aide de laquelle on détermine les inégalités séculaires des mouvements des planètes. *In Oeuvres Complètes (II^{ème} Série)*, 9.
- Chawla, U., Shaw, J., & Choudhary, S. (2022). Streaming apps-A study on consumer satisfaction toward the usage of these platforms during COVID-19 in Kolkata, West Bengal. *Indian Journal of Marketing*, 52(10), 33-49.
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). Sampling techniques. *John Wiley & Sons*.
- Chung, N., Song, H. G., & Lee, H. (2017). Consumers' impulsive buying behavior of restaurant products in social commerce. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(2), 709-73.

- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2003). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. 11.0 update (4th ed.)*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon
- Godlee, F. (2010). Conflicts of Interest and Pandemic Flu, *British Medical Journal Publishing Group*, vol. 340 (2010), p. c2947
- Girija, S., Sharma, D. R., & Kaushal, V. (2022). Exploring dimensions of the customer experience at budget hotels during the COVID-19 pandemic: a netnography approach. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, (ahead-of-print).
- Grattan-Guinness, I. (1997). *The rainbow of mathematics*. New York: Norton.
- Hotelling, H. (1933). Analysis of a complex of statistical variables into principal components. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 25, 417–441.
- Jackson, J.E. (1991). *A user's guide to principal components*. New York: Wiley.
- Jolliffe, I.T. (2002). *Principal component analysis*. New York: Springer.
- Jordan, C. (1874). M'emoire sur les formes bilinéaires. *Journal de Mathématiques Pures et Appliquées*, 19, 35–54.
- Kobayashi, Y., & Anbumozhi, V. (2016). Cooperation framework for oil stockpiling and emergency response system.
- Liren, X., Junmei, C., & Mingqin, Z. (2012). Research on panic purchase's behavior mechanism. *Innovation and Management*.
- Mandal, T. (2021). Consumer Research Process and Understanding Buying Behavior Post COVID-19, *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*, 5(10), 186-192.
- Mondal, R., Kotal, S., & Ghosh, R. (2023). Reviewing the Factors Distressing Consumers Buying Behaviour During COVID-19 Pandemic with Special Reference to Kolkata using Principal Component Analysis. *Management Journal for Advanced Research*, 3(2), 1-11.
- Pearson, K. (1901). On lines and planes of closest fit to systems of points in space. *Philosophical Magazine*, 6, 559–572.
- Rajeswari, P & Vijai, C. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Consumers behaviour in India. 45. 2249-6661.
- Sharma, A., & Jhamb, D. (2020). Changing consumer behaviours towards online shopping-an impact of Covid 19. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 24(3), 1-10.
- Sheth, J. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on consumer behavior: Will the old habits return or die? *Journal of business research*, 117, 280-283.
- Shivaprasad, A. R. H. (2021). Revisiting the antecedent of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) during COVID-19 Pandemic, 48(4), 419–432.
- Shou, B., Xiong, H., & Shen, X. (2013). Consumer panic buying and quota policy under supply disruptions. *Manuf. Serv. Oper. Manag.*, 6, 1-9.

Singh, K., & Basu, R. Online Consumer Shopping Behaviour: A Review and Research Agenda. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 47(3), 815-851.

Saporta, G., & Niang, N. (2009). Principal component analysis: application to statistical process control. In G. Govaert (Ed), *Data analysis*. (pp. 1–23). London: *Wiley*.

Srivastava, P. R., Sengupta, K., Kumar, A., Biswas, B., & Ishizaka, A. (2022). Post-epidemic factors influencing customer's booking intent for a hotel or leisure spot: an empirical study. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 35(1), 78-99.

Yuen, K. F., Wang, X., Ma, F., & Li, K. X. (2020). The psychological causes of panic buying following a health crisis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(10), 3513.

<https://www.kmcgov.in/KMCPortal/jsp/KMCPortalHome1.jsp>

<https://scholarworks.iupui.edu/bitstream/handle/1805/344/gliem+&+gliem.pdf?sequence=1>

https://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/mph-modules/bs/bs704_nonparametric/bs704_nonparametric4.html